

LEGAL NORMS OF INTERACTION BETWEEN MAHALLA INSTITUTIONS AND STATE AUTHORITIES PROBLEMS OF IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract. Amendments and additions to the law on the interaction between mahalla institutions and state authorities, and on the election of citizens' assembly chairpersons, are necessary. It is stated that the organisation and conduct of elections should be supplemented with new principles, as should the representation of citizens.

Key words: Elections for mahalla institutions, the constitution, state authorities and citizens' assembly chairpersons.

In a traditional society, the main moral norm for residents of the mahalla is to comply with the community's behavioural rules. These are our traditions. The mahalla is firmly embedded in Uzbek culture [1].

The mahalla institution is a social institution formed by the public and operating in cooperation with the state. It represents the social, cultural, economic and legal interests of a given population or territory, and is aimed at protecting and regulating them. It incorporates traditional and modern management mechanisms and functions of social control.

Cooperation between the mahalla and state bodies involves interaction between mahalla institutions and state authorities. This implies joint activities in areas such as social management, maintaining public order, providing social services and protecting citizens' interests. This cooperation is based on the distribution of powers, responsibilities and resources within the system of social relations and legal norms.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 3 February this year, 'On Measures for Further Improvement of the Mahalla Institute', establishes the legal basis for this structure and sets out its key objectives, which include transforming the mahalla into a structure that is closest to and most oriented towards the population, and further developing cooperation with state bodies and civil society institutions.

It is known that our ancestors initially engaged in economic activities naturally. The mahalla served as a market of sorts, directing its inhabitants towards the production or cultivation of certain products and facilitating their mutual exchange. Narrow economic ties forced community members to coordinate their activities with others and produce goods necessary for the

mahalla. For this reason, even after thousands of years, mahallas have not lost their significance in socio-economic relations. The state is consistently improving the procedure for organising citizens' self-government activities, strengthening their legal foundations [2].

A Model Plan is currently in effect by the Supreme Council. However, this Model Plan does not comply with current legislation. This is because the commissions established in the Plan have changed completely. In our opinion, the Council of Ministers should develop and approve a 'Model Regulation' on the citizens' assembly of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Further enhancing the role of the mahalla in our socio-economic life will remain at the centre of our attention. To this end, the citizens' assembly of the mahalla will be granted the right to submit proposals to sessions of the local council of people's deputies in its territory, and to participate in the development and discussion of the council's draft decisions. To identify and solve social problems that cause discontent among the population, the following practices will be established: - monthly discussions with the mahalla chairman - monthly reports from the heads of relevant state bodies and organisations at the mahalla council. The institutions of 'mahalla control' and 'mahalla chairman's inquiry' will also be introduced.

Regulation of relations on the organization and conduct of elections of chairpersons (aksakals) of citizens' assemblies is aimed at ensuring the exercise of citizens' rights in the manner prescribed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In accordance with Article 99 of the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan: In settlements and mahallas, as well as in cities and their mahallas, citizens' assemblies are bodies of self-government which elect a chairman (aksakal).

The Law of the Republic of Karakalpakstan "On the Election of the Chairperson of the Citizens' Assembly", adopted on 27 March 2019, regulates the procedure for organising and conducting elections for the chairperson of the citizens' assembly. According to Article 9 of this law: 'State bodies assist citizens' assemblies in organising and conducting elections for the chairperson of the citizens' assembly and, if necessary, must provide them with premises, transport and communication facilities.' Therefore, state authorities and administrations must provide practical assistance to citizens' assemblies in organising and conducting elections for chairpersons of citizens' assemblies. The Jokargy Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is involved in determining the

procedure for elections to citizens' self-government bodies and in approving the composition of the Republican Commission.

On 24 March 2022, in accordance with Article 99 of the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan [3], Article 23 of the Law 'On Citizens' Self-Government Bodies', Article 57 of the Law 'On the Regulations of the Jokargy Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan', and Articles 8, 10 and 11, and 12 of the Law 'On Elections of the Chairperson (Aksakal) of the Citizens' Assembly', and in connection with the expiration of the term of office of the chairpersons of citizens' assemblies in May 2022. This was also in accordance with the Resolution of the Presidium of the Jokargy Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan No. QQ-320-IV 'On the preparation and conduct of elections of chairpersons (aksakals) of citizens' assemblies', the resolution of the Presidium of the Jokargy Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan № 639 was adopted.

Legal scholar D.D. Shalyagin notes that the social service role of the US police is increasing year by year [4]. To encourage citizens to play an active role in maintaining law and order, the police use various methods, such as providing attractive uniforms, rewarding their work in different ways, organising free events, offering monetary incentives, delivering speeches in the media and announcing gratitude from senior state officials [5].

The voluntary police service in Germany has been operating since 1963. Those who have undergone two weeks of preliminary training and been tested for their ability to perform police duties are admitted to the service, with 10–15 people forming one group [6]. Volunteer police service members provide close assistance to the police in situations such as mass riots and the search for missing persons. They are paid a monetary reward for this work [7].

To effectively ensure public participation in maintaining public order and security, and in preventing offences, the Russian Federation has created the necessary legal framework, which includes The Federal Law 'On the Participation of Citizens in the Protection of Public Order' (dated 2 April 2014), as well as over 500 territorial regulatory legal acts [8].

It should be noted that regular cooperation between the police and the public in ensuring public order and security can achieve the following:

Firstly, it can ensure law and order at the local level and effectively maintain public order and security.

Secondly, it can establish effective public control over the activities of police bodies.

Thirdly, it can demonstrate that both the police and the public are responsible for ensuring public order and security in the region and preventing offences.

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